

A Study of Expanding Role of Women in Socio-Economic Development of Modern India

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Abstract

While glorifying Indian Women, late prime minister Indira Gandhi had stated that no society could progress if half its members did not have equal opportunity and their talents and capabilities were ignored. Indian culture and religion have placed women on high pedestal of sublimity. UNO's universal declaration of human rights and Indian constitution eloquently provide for equal rights to men and women and any discrimination based on sex, caste, race etc. is unconstitutional. It is discomfoting to observe that Indian women have long been subjected to all sorts of subjugation, humiliations, deprivations, suppression, torture and atrocities. Right through history, Indian women had been confined to home making and house hold keeping. The perception of patriarchal society of the country has been that women are physically weaker than men, squeamish and unable to perform work effectively and hence cannot shoulder the rigors of administrative and managerial responsibilities along with domestic chores. However, the modern Indian society is in a phase of transition where women emancipation started in nineteenth century. Now we have women in all walks of life in contemporary society, who work shoulder to shoulder with their men counterparts. Several myths about women were broken by the beginning of twenty first century.

In this paper the author attempts to examine and analyze how women have broken the glass ceiling and have displayed their capabilities in different fields in modern times.

KeyWords :Chauvinistic, Emancipation, Empowerment, Glass ceiling, Public administration, Women entrepreneurs.

Backdrop

The modern Indian society is in a phase of transition where women emancipation started in nineteenth century. Now we have women in all walks of life in contemporary society, who work shoulder to shoulder with their men counterparts. Several myths about women were broken by the beginning of twenty first century.

Objectives of the study

1. To examine how modern women of India have cut across the boundaries of their homes and excelled in different areas shouldering the responsibility of nation building along with their male counterparts.
2. To throw light on various issues and challenges the women are facing at their work places.
3. To give solutions for overcoming the challenges so that their competitiveness and efficiency in all walks of life can give the best outcomes.

Research Methodology

The present study is based on secondary data collection. The secondary data was collected from various published sources like Demographic and Health Surveys, Human Development Report, Books, Journals, Newspaper clippings, internet websites etc.

Emerging role of Indian Women in Economic Development

The decades post liberalization and globalization have witnessed subtle transformation in the traditional role of women who are

increasingly and successfully moving into mainstream of development. Indian women are becoming visible in politics, civil administration, art and architecture, literature, and more recently, in business and profession. As a result the proportion of population of working women has surged significantly from 13% in 1987 to 23% in 2022. Many women are making inexorable efforts to break glass ceiling to redefine the concept of women, frame their own paradigms and grab with delight the emerging opportunities and display their shiny performance to make their presence felt domestically and globally as well in every male dominated bastion.

Gradual but steady increase in women's role in India's corporate sector

The status of India as a growing powerhouse is gaining momentum since the last decade with the changing pace of gender diversity being witnessed in modern times. Thankfully, India does not suffer much from the caste-profession matching problem today. Current lot of women managers have been identified as empathetic, supportive, relationship builder, power sharing and information sharing. Compared to male counterparts, women managers are more meticulous, careful, patient and co-operative. Corporate India in the recent times has been emphasizing on gender diversity and has been making policies to hire more women in 2023. Leading organisations such as Cognizant, Larsen & Toubro and HDFC Bank have

initiated several measures to attract more women employees like flexible work hours and mentoring programmes. Indian women are occupying senior positions in managerial hierarchy of banking sector and exhibiting cosmic performance. Ms. Leena Nair, Global Chief Executive Officer of Chanel, Ms. Roshni Nadar, Chairperson of HCL Technologies, Ms. Sharmistha Dubey, CEO of Match Group, Ms. Revathi Advaiti, CEO, Flex are the current lot of Indian top corporate women leading the global companies and have earned well deserved recognition across the world for their outstanding performance, exhibit of intelligence and wisdom in leading these companies.

Increasing participation of women in public administration

There was a time when the voice of Indian women could hardly reach the public sphere. Women had no right to work and were suppressed by the big guns of the society. But there has been a paradigm shift in Indian society with time, and the once deprived section is slowly infiltrating the most prestigious services of our country. During the last few years, the participation of women in top administrative jobs has seen significant increase and their performance in discharging their duties with committed perseverance and determination has caught the public eye. Some of the most notable women who have proved that they are no less than men when it came to be shouldering the responsibilities of nation's building and progress are Ms. Anna Rajam George; first IAS officer of independent India, Ms. Kiran Bedi; the first woman IPS officer, Dr. Ruveda Salam ; the first woman from Kashmir to crack the IAS examination in 2013 who has earned countless accolades for working tirelessly in reducing the crime rate in the state, Ms. Ira Singhal ; the first physically challenged woman to crack the civil service exam in general category. It is perceived that women would feel more comfortable in presence of other women and their self-respect can be taken care of in a better way.

Emergence of women entrepreneurs

The first wave of women entrepreneurs after independence increased due to new economic reforms as accessibility to credit facilities have become easy and fast. There has been rapid growth of women entrepreneurs in world of fashion, beauty, textiles, art, hospitality, media and entertainment sectors. These entrepreneurs have established their own Startups in India and have become the job providers to thousands of people despite countless problems. Some of them are Ms. Chitra Gurnani Daga, CEO of Thrillophilia, India's biggest platform for booking travel experiences, Ms. Upasana Taku, Co-founder of MobiKwik & Zaakpay which is the mobile based payment service provider, Ms. Aditi

Gupta, founder of Menstrupedia, a company which aims at creating menstrual awareness, Ms Divya Gokulnath, Co-founder of one of India's largest ed-tech start-ups Byju's, Ms. Suchi Mukherjee, founder and CEO of Limeroad, an Indian online clothing firm, Ms Falguni Nayar, founder and CEO of Nykaa.

Role of women in medical and engineering services

Since ancient times, be it herbal remedies, alternative medicine, or midwifery, women have proved that they are the natural caregivers despite more numbers of men in the profession. Some of the leading Indian women who have made exceptional contributions in the field of medical science are Dr. Anandibai Joshi, Dr. Ketayun Ardeshir Dinshaw, Dr. Indira Hinduja, Dr. Manjula Anagani, Dr. Gagandeep Kang. In the field of technology and innovation, it has been proved that women can bring a fresh approach and offer unique perspectives to meet challenges, solve problems, and design new products. Empirical study reveals that although across the globe, the gap between women working in IT is much smaller than that of men, in the Indian context the efforts towards empowering women in the IT sector are showing results. At present India's IT sector is recruiting and retaining more women and assigning them more leadership roles. NASSCOM estimates that nearly 60 percent of Indian IT firms have 20 percent women at the C-Suite level. Companies reported a 4.5 percent higher proportion of young women aged between 30 and 35 in C-Suite roles than men in the same age group. Some of the leading Indian women in field of technology are Ms. Saloni Vijay, General Manager, IT, Vodafone Idea Ltd, Mayurakshi Ray, Chief compliance officer, GeBBS, Health care Solutions, Geetha Kanan, Founder and CEO of Wequity for Women and Technology, Annie John Matthew, Chief Information Officer, Mother Dairy, Fruit and Vegetables Pvt Ltd, Ms. Amrita Gangotra, Global Strategic Advisor, Digital and IT Transformation, Growth strategist and Tech Start-ups.

Challenges before Women Workforce in Corporate sector and administration in India

The continuing pervasive under representation of Indian women in managerial positions, persistent gender discrimination in selection, promotion, and compensation, perpetuation of harassment of women at workplace and creation of invisible barriers that prevent talented women from advancing past a certain level are likely to prove suicidal to the economic and industrial development of the nation in highly globalized competitive milieu which has come to stay. One of the key factors responsible for low competitiveness of Indian corporates despite existence of vast reservoir of intellectual capital

including professionally qualified women constituting world's largest number is the failure of top management in utilizing fully the existing talents and continuously creating and developing pool of talents of both men and women. The majority of companies have so far failed to create true equal opportunity workplace that is completely gender neutral, where management is blind to gender while selecting people for job position, promotion, training and development and where merit and performance matter.

Despite the legislative sanctions against sex discrimination and immense array of such programmes, progress towards gender equality for women in organization has been far slower than expected. Discrimination against employees including managers and execution in workplace is a continuing problem across the country. It takes essentially three forms, viz; overt discrimination in hiring women, paying them inequitably and promoting them, causing virulent harassment to women and forcing them to leave the organization. Women have to work harder than men to prove their competence all the time and to earn equal to their male counterparts. The glass ceiling is the third form of discrimination in which invisible barriers are created to prevent women from advancing past a certain level. Thus, the process of gender equality and women empowerment still has a long way to go and may even have become more difficult in the recent past. This is despite explicit moves of the Government.

Recommendations

In order to make Indian women potential effective source of competitive advantage and corporate growth, a number of micro-level organizational as well as individual efforts need to be made. First of all, organizations have to become gender neutral employers to provide equal opportunity to men and women and to ensure that merit and performance alone are the criteria for recognition and growth. This can be done through formulation of crystal clear human resource policies and their meticulous execution. Secondly, while creating a gender-neutral workplace, organizations must be sensitive to specific problems of women managers. Women do have special responsibilities of rearing children and caring for family members. So as to ensure that the organization does not lose talented women because of these compulsions, the former should creatively address this issue with flexi work schedules, longer leave periods and fuller use of technology to reduce the need of women to be physically present in the office for work. Institutional efforts are also required to provide for fully equipped creches to nurse infants. The persistence of sexual harassment despite efforts to curb it through legislative and organizational

policies and actions points to the critical need for innovative strategies. Increasing representation of women at the executive levels in organizations could be one such strategy. It is also ineluctable to create a climate of intolerance and the one that supports employee growth, participation and empowerment through training, mentoring programmes and equitable pay for all employees.

Conclusion

The world at the end of the 20th century and so our country have gone through a subtle revolution which has changed the traditional relationship of women to work and the family resulting in an expanded role for women in the global market place. Indian corporates in their relentless drive to enhance their competitiveness have accepted the fact that without best utilizing the women resources they cannot achieve competitive advantage and sustain competitive superiority over their rivals. Hence they have gone all out to provide the most suitable opportunities and effective platforms to young women. In 2022, a survey among 250 Indian companies revealed that the share of women in CEO roles in India reached 55%, which was more than double the global average of 24%. This goes to show that there is a slow but steady transformation in organizational culture and mindsets of top management and structured interventions are being made to ensure gender neutral human resource policies and actions.

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